

DECONSOLIDATION IN COMPOSITE PROCESSING: COMPARISON OF TWO GLASS FIBER-POLYPROPYLENE SYSTEMS

J. Wolfrath, V. Michaud and J.-A. E. Månson

*Laboratoire de Technologie des Composites et Polymères (LTC),
Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland*

ABSTRACT

In thermoplastic based composite processing, a molten matrix impregnates a dry fiber preform producing preconsolidated blanks. These composites parts are afterwards subjected to post-processing, which consists in reheating followed by stamping or flow molding. During reheating, the material generally lofts, and its void content increases. In this paper, the phenomena leading to deconsolidation are thus investigated, with particular emphasis on the elastic release of stress in the preform, also called spring-back effect. A model is proposed to simulate the kinetics of the phenomenon and the evolution of the specimen thickness. A comparison with model experiments is also provided. Finally, a comparison of two different initial material structures of glass mat and polypropylene is proposed. Deconsolidation experiments of a classical type of GMT and a new type of commingled system are carried out. It is shown that for both systems the void increase due to deconsolidation exceeds 50%. It can be then concluded that if the fiber volume fraction is identical and homogenous in the structure, the void increase due to deconsolidation is the same. Furthermore, the model experiments of springback have shown that void formation plays a major role in deconsolidation and is induced by the lofting of the fiber preform: when the fiber preform tends to recover its initial relaxed thickness, tensile forces are induced in the molten matrix which lead to void growth.

KEYWORDS: Impregnation, Consolidation, Deconsolidation, Glass Mat reinforced Thermoplastics.

INTRODUCTION

During composite processing, in general, a dry fiber preform is impregnated by a matrix. The impregnated part is sometimes used as produced, but most often requires a post-processing step, either a post-cure, in the case of thermoset-based composites or a reheating stage before stamping or flow molding for thermoplastic-based composites. This step may lead to the release of the locked-in stresses, often called lofting or deconsolidation. The part dimensions and void content then increase, and the fiber volume fraction decreases. In the case of thermoset-based composite, this should be avoided because it results in a low quality part, so post-curing is performed so as to retain the matrix mechanical properties. In the case of thermoplastic samples, which are post-formed, lofting is often considered as a necessary step, but one may ask if it is cost-effective to fully impregnate the fiber preform in the first step, since pressure will be applied again at a later stage. These issues have often been noticed, sometimes reported [1], but not yet quantified. The parameters governing deconsolidation are the *process* (processing temperature or the applied pressure) and the *initial material structure and behavior* such as the type of the fiber arrangement or the matrix initial dispersion and viscosity at processing temperature.

In this paper, two different types of process are studied: the Consolidation Process and the Infiltration Process. Both are diagrammatically represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Difference between Consolidation and Infiltration processes.

In the consolidation process, matrix and reinforcement are already mixed, and air is evacuated by the application of pressure. In the infiltration process, the fluid matrix impregnates a dry preform. The main difference between these two processes lies in the distance the matrix covers to provide impregnation, which is shorter in the consolidation process.

Related to those two processes, two material systems are studied: a commingled system made of premixed glass and polypropylene fibers (*Quadrant Plastic Composites, Switzerland*) and a more classical type of Glass Mat Reinforced Thermoplastic composite (GMT) made of initially separated polypropylene resin and glass fiber mat. During processing, the load sharing is different for both systems: in the case of commingled systems, the resin hydrostatically supports the load whereas in the case of GMT, the fiber network first compresses under the applied load and the load is then progressively shared between the resin and the fiber preform [2-4].

The influence of these structural differences on impregnation and deconsolidation phenomena is investigated experimentally, as a function of applied pressure, viscosity and processing time. A model to predict the spring-back effect is presented, based on the solution of the equations governing fluid and mass transport. The theoretical results are then discussed in light of the experimental data.

MATERIALS

For the classical GMT, a polypropylene matrix containing a blend of homopolymer and ethylene propylene rubber having a viscosity of 260 Pa·s at 200°C and at a frequency of 1·rad·s⁻¹ was used. The matrix behavior remained Newtonian during impregnation as the shear rate did not exceed 1s⁻¹.

The *mat*, manufactured by Quadrant Plastic Composite AG, is a 2D needled glass fibers structure. Fiber length is about 50mm and each bundle contains about 100 fibers. The surface density is 600g/m². A final GMT blank has a typical fiber volume fraction of 13%.

For the commingled system, the polypropylene has a viscosity similar to the GMT polypropylene and is in the shape of fibers with a diameter of about 15 μm. The surface density of the commingled system is 700g/cm³. The fiber volume fraction is 13% in the final product as well.

Furthermore, a model matrix consisting of polyethylene glycol (PEG, Fluka®, M_w=35'000 g/mol) mixed with water is used to perform permeability measurements at room temperature. The PEG/water blends have a varying viscosity depending on the PEG and water proportions. Its behavior is fully Newtonian and it is easy to handle. The viscosity ranges from 0.13 to 6 Pa·s.

The difference between the commingled system made of pre-mixed fibers of polypropylene and glass and the classical type of GMT consists in a different load sharing between the matrix and the fiber preform. In the case of the commingled system, when the structure is heated at processing temperature, the polypropylene fibers will melt and then hydrostatically support the load. Figure 2 represents the states before (A) and after (B) melting of the polypropylene fibers:

Figure 2: Microstructure of commingled structure A) at the initial state and B) after melting of the polypropylene, that is to say just before compression.

An initial structure made of polypropylene and glass fibers is, after heating a different structure made of glass fibers porous medium containing agglomerates of melted matrix. If the structure is compressed, the glass fibers will be brought together and the matrix will support the load. In the case of the classical type of GMT, the fiber preform is first compressed and then infiltrated by the matrix. It has been observed that the time for full infiltration is shorter than the time necessary for the fiber volume fraction to relax and the reinforcement distribution to homogenize [3]. Then, an apparently well-impregnated part may exhibit an inhomogeneous distribution of the reinforcement affecting the residual stress distribution. This inhomogeneous structure may also increase the deconsolidation effect. However, if the impregnation time is large enough to provide full relaxation of the reinforcement, the deconsolidation behavior of the GMT should not differ from that of the commingled system.

THEORY

There are three main contributions to deconsolidation: first, the elastic behavior of the fiber preform, which tends to recover its initial position. Secondly, void formation and growth [5] and finally, the viscoelastic behavior of the matrix, which may affect the deconsolidation.

In this paper, we concentrate our effort on the elastic behavior of the fiber preform also called the springback effect, which often represents the major contribution. The compressibility of the fiber preform influences the impregnation by increasing the fiber volume fraction and then decreasing the permeability but also plays a major role in the deconsolidation phenomena. The compressed preform embedded in the solid matrix tends to recover its initial position when the matrix melts at processing temperature. The compressive behavior through the compression curve is then an important characteristic of the dry preform and should be taken into account in the impregnation and deconsolidation modeling.

The deconsolidation modeling is inspired by the impregnation model of Michaud *et al.* [3]. The main assumptions are that we can neglect the lateral frictions between the mold walls and the side of the preform, the capillary forces at the infiltration front as well as the body and inertial forces. We assume for simplicity the matrix behavior to be Newtonian, so that the Darcy's law is valid.

The main equations related to these phenomena are:

- **Darcy's law:**
$$u_l - u_s = -\frac{K}{\eta(1-V_f)} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

- **Mass conservation of the solid:**
$$\frac{\partial V_f}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(V_f u_s)}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (2)$$

and of the liquid:
$$-\frac{\partial V_f}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial((1-V_f)u_l)}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (3)$$

- **Conservation of body forces:**
$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial x} = -\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial x} \quad (4)$$

where u_l is the average local velocity of the liquid within the pores, u_s is the local velocity of the solid, K the permeability of the porous medium, P the pressure in the liquid, η the matrix viscosity, V_f is the fiber volume fraction, and σ the stress.

The equation describing the evolution of V_f with time t and distance x is thus the highly non linear equation which follows:

$$\frac{\partial V_f}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(V_f \frac{K}{\eta} \frac{d\sigma}{dV_f} \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial x} \right) = 0 \quad (5)$$

The three system parameters to measure are the viscosity, the permeability $K=f(V_f)$ and the term $\frac{d\sigma}{dV_f}$ which represents the compressive behavior of the fiber preform.

The initial state corresponds to a layer of melted polypropylene placed on a fiber preform. Then, when pressure is applied, the preform compresses and starts to be infiltrated. Simultaneously, the preform relaxes. The equilibrium step represents the case where the preform reaches the other hand of the mold before relaxing completely. The last step is the deconsolidation. If we assume that deconsolidation occurs only because of the springback effect of the fiber network, having the matrix unaffected, the equations governing deconsolidation are exactly the same as those describing infiltration and relaxation. These equations are solved numerically with a finite difference scheme written in Fortran.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Two different kinds of experiments are carried out: *model experiments* of springback and experiments of *consolidation and deconsolidation* of commingled structures and GMT.

The model experiments are carried out with glass mat and polyethylene glycol blends. Round pieces of 56mm diameter of glass mat are cut and placed in a transparent cylinder. The fibers are then immersed in PEG/water blends of viscosity varying between 0.13 and 6 Pa·s. In parallel, the viscosity of the matrix is precisely measured with Couette set-up in a rotational rheometer (Rheometrics, RDA II) before each experiment. A piston is then used to compress the layers of mat until a desired fiber volume fraction, which is usually taken as 13% in order to approach industrial values of consolidated GMT blanks.

Once the mat immersed and compressed, the piston is removed and the video camera systems allow to follow the evolution of the stack of mats as a function of time. Two different situations are tested: a completely immersed case where the mats are saturated of PEG solution and a more realistic experiment where the exact amount of PEG is used in order to observe void formation. The set-up is given in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Set-up used for springback measurements.

Consolidation/Deconsolidation experiments of GMT are carried out by placing polypropylene at the bottom of a previously heated closed mold (200°C). Two layers of glass mat are placed on it. A pressure of 2 bars at 200°C is then applied for 10 minutes. Rapid cooling (10°C/min) is then carried out under pressure. Two superposed mats are used in order to provide a large enough impregnation distance for the clear measurement of macroscopic impregnation, as well as about the same weight of final parts. The closed mold offers the advantage of providing boundary conditions resembling those in the central part of a double belt press, with constant temperature and pressure and no transverse flow.

In order to provide resembling industrial reheating conditions, the sample are freely placed on an aluminum sheet in an oven at 200°C for 10 minutes. Rapid cooling is carried out at room temperature. For the void content analysis, the samples were mounted under vacuum in an epoxy matrix to fill the voids, and polished up to 4000 grit SiC paper and then with AP-A 1µm alumina polishing suspension (*Struers*). Image analysis was then performed with an Olympus BH-2 with a Sony CCD-IRS black and white camera attached. An image analysis software, Image Tool, has been used to determine the fiber and void volume fractions.

RESULTS

Model experiments

The evolution of 4 different front positions from 4 mats individually marked along the mat thickness is given in Figure 4A, and a comparison of the upper front position for two different PEG/water blends viscosities is given in Figure 4B.

A)

B)

Figure 4: A) Four front positions evolution as a function of time for a resin viscosity of 5.92 Pa·s. B) upper front position evolution as a function of time for two different resin viscosities: 0.13 Pa·s (low) and 5.92 Pa·s (high).

Whereas Figure 4a gives the tendency of the front evolution of different positions in the layer of mat, Figure 4b shows that a higher viscosity induces a slower relaxation of the preform. It is also shown that in case of high viscosity, the preform does not recover completely its initial position: a part of the locked-in stresses are not released after 900 sec.

Another test has been carried out in order to measure the effect of the void growth: instead of using a large amount of resin so that the fiber preform is immersed, the exact amount of matrix in order to obtain 13% glass fiber volume fraction when compressed has been used. The results are given in Figure 5. The PEG/water blend has in this case a viscosity of 0.13 Pa·s.

Figure 5: Evolution of the adimensional height of the preform versus time for two different cases: immersed (A) and non-immersed (B) fiber preform.

It is observed that, in case of use of the exact amount of matrix, the kinetics of the phenomena are faster. In the completely immersed case, the presence of PEG slows down the kinetics. With the exact amount of resin, voids are formed in the liquid matrix and grow under the tensile stresses imposed by the moving preform, thereby enhancing the kinetics of preform relaxation.

Finally, a comparison of the evolution of the height of the preform for the completely immersed case and a resin viscosity of 5.92 Pa·s with the model is given in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Model and experimental results versus time for a PEG/water blend of viscosity equals 5.92 Pa·s.

The tendency is in agreement with the modeling but the model overestimates the springback effect. This is mainly due to friction effect on mold walls that slows down the process.

Consolidation/Deconsolidation experiments

Microstructures of consolidated and deconsolidated GMT composites are shown in Figure 7. The void volume fraction of the consolidated specimen is about 2.1%, whereas this value increases up to 51.3% for the deconsolidated part. The large voids are observed to take place between the fiber bundles.

Figure 7: Microstructure of consolidated and deconsolidated GMT parts. Voids are seen in light grey.

The evolution of porosity at the initial, preconsolidated, deconsolidated and reconsolidated states is given in Figure 8. The porosity is observed to decrease from an initial value of 95.2% corresponding to a dry preform to a value of 2.1%. Then, the deconsolidation step implies a porosity increase to 51.3%, value which decrease to 1.2% for the final re-consolidated state. The evolution of the fiber volume fraction is also given and is observed to follow logically the inverse tendency.

Figure 8: Fiber and void volume fraction evolution through the processing steps: initial dry state, preconsolidated, deconsolidated and reconsolidated stages.

A comparative plate of pure Polypropylene was processed and deconsolidated in the same conditions and has shown a void content increase of 1.5%. This void content increase is negligible in comparison with the 50% void content of the deconsolidated GMT structure. This indicates that the void increase is mainly due to the springback effect. The driving force due to the de-compaction of the fiber preform will drive the microscopic voids already existing in the polymer matrix to grow due to the tensile effect. There is thus a correlation between the springback and the void growth. Deconsolidation experiments in the same conditions have also been carried out for the commingled system. Figure 9 gives a microscopic representation of the consolidated and deconsolidated structures.

Figure 9: Microstructures of consolidated (A) and deconsolidated (B) commingled systems, voids are seen in light grey.

A value of 58% void content has been measured and is in accordance with the 51% of the deconsolidated classical GMT. An identical pore volume fraction after deconsolidation for both structures means that the fiber volume fraction and the stress distribution in the parts are the same. In order to verify the fiber volume fraction corresponding to an applied pressure value of 2 bars, compressive curves of the dry preform are necessary. A typical compressive curve of dry glass mat for the GMT is given in Figure 10 A). In the case of the commingled system, since the structure is made of pre-mixed polypropylene and glass fibers, the mat has been burnt at high temperature in order to remove any matrix and sizing. The mat was then tested in compression and the result is given in Figure 10 B).

Figure 10: Compressive curve of glass mat (A) and burnt commingled system (B).

For a stress value of 0.2 MPa, the fiber volume fraction of the dry glass mat is about 0.23 and for the burnt commingled system, the value is about 0.19. This slight difference should imply a higher deconsolidation after reheating for the GMT, but the measured values do not show this trend. However, the behavior of the relaxation part (down arrow in Fig.10A)) differs for the two different

systems: the dry mat has a more elastic behavior. Once compressed, the fiber preform of the commingled system remains to a higher volume fraction (0.15 instead of 0.05 for the dry preform). This information means that even if the preform does not recover completely its initial position when the stress is removed, void content after deconsolidation is unchanged. It can then be inferred that the relaxed preform thickness does not really influence deconsolidation. The voids need a threshold pressure level to grow. Once this pressure level reached, void growth is generated and is then not sensitive to the final value of V_f . This needs to be verified with quasi-static compression experiments on the commingled system, as the burnt material may exhibit a less lubricated behavior [6, 7].

CONCLUSION

This article investigated the deconsolidation mechanisms of glass mat reinforced thermoplastics. A model is presented to simulate the kinetics of the deconsolidation and is compared with model experiments. It is shown that the springback effect is dependent on matrix viscosity but also on void formation due to tensile forces in the matrix induced by the elastic behavior of the preform. The model shows good agreement with the experimental results. Furthermore, a comparison in terms of deconsolidation between two different material systems is provided. Consolidation and deconsolidation experiments of a classical type of GMT and a new type of commingled polypropylene and glass fibers have been carried out. Void content measurements have shown that the deconsolidation of both systems is identical. This observation as well as compressive curves analysis allow us to affirm that the deconsolidation phenomena is mainly due to the springback effect but that the induced tensile forces generate void formation and growth.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is supported by the Fonds National de la Recherche Scientifique under contract no. 2000-067947.02. The authors gratefully acknowledge Quadrant Plastic Composites for donating material and V. Mathier for taking part in the work during his study.

REFERENCES

1. HENNINGER, F., L. YE, and K. FRIEDRICH, *Deconsolidation behaviour of glass fibre-polyamide 12 composite sheet material during post-processing*. *Plastics, Rubber and Composites Processing and Applications*, 1998. **27**(6): p. 287-292.
2. TOLL, S., *Elastic compression of the fiber network*. *Journal of applied mechanics*, 1995. **62**: p. 223-226.
3. MICHAUD, V., R. TORNQVIST, and J.-A. MANSON, *Impregnation of compressible fiber mats with a thermoplastic resin. Part I: Theory*. *Journal of composite materials*, 2000.
4. MICHAUD, V., R. TORNQVIST, and J.-A. MANSON, *Impregnation of compressible fiber mats with a thermoplastic resin. Part II: Experiments*. *Journal of composite materials*, 2000.
5. YE, L., M. LU, and Y.-W. MAI, *Thermal de-consolidation of thermoplastic matrix composites-I. Growth of voids*. *Composite Science and Technology*, 2002. **62**: p. 2121-2130.
6. KIM, Y.R., S.P. McCARTHY, and J.P. FANUCCI, *Compressibility and relaxation of fiber reinforcement during composite processing*. *Polymer Composites*, 1991. **12**(1): p. 13-19.
7. SERVAIS, C., V. MICHAUD, and J.-A.E. MANSON, *The packing stress of impregnated fiber mats*. *Polymer Composites*, 2001. **22**(2): p. 298-311.